

This are the supplementary materials for the pre-peer reviewed version of the following article:

Native aquatic plastispheres in a river–wastewater catchment: carbapenem-resistant bacteria isolation and microscopy-based structural analysis

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Native aquatic plastispheres in a river–wastewater catchment: Structural and microbial characterization using microscopy and culture-based methods

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Figure S1 Field photographs taken during sample collection for wastewater (A–E) and river (F). Red arrows indicate visible plastic fragments observed on the sieves and directly in the environment.

Table S1 Numerical summary of bacterial strains classified for microbiological analyses, isolated from individual plastic particles. Characteristics of classified particles — analyzed (identified) and those with confirmed carbapenem resistance.
 *Particles excluded from further analysis due to lack of growth on Carba medium.

Site	Source	Piece ID	No. of colonies piecked for analyses				Failed to reculture	No. of colonies analysed				Confirmaed imipenem resistance	
			Total	22	37	Carba		Total	22	37	Carba		
2W	Wastewater	2.3	9	3	3	3	1	8	3	3	2	1	
2W	Wastewater	2.8	9	3	3	3	4	5	2	3	0	0	
3W	Wastewater	3.1	9	3	3	3	3	6	3	3	0	0	
5W	Wastewater	5.1	9	3	3	3	2	7	3	3	1	0	
6W	Wastewater	6.4	9	3	3	3	1	8	3	3	2	0	
6W	Wastewater	6.7	9	3	3	3	3	6	3	3	0	0	
6W	Wastewater	6.9	9	3	3	3	3	6	3	2	1	1	
6W	Wastewater	6.11	9	3	3	3	2	7	2	3	2	2	
12W	Wastewater	12.1	9	3	3	3	7	2	0	2	0	0	
12W	Wastewater	12.6	0	EXCLUDED*									
12W	Wastewater	12.8	9	3	3	3	6	3	1	2	0	0	
20W	Wastewater	20.5	9	3	3	3	6	3	1	2	0	0	
20W	Wastewater	20.6	9	3	3	3	3	6	2	3	1	1	
20W	Wastewater	20.11	9	3	3	3	4	5	2	2	1	1	
22W	Wastewater	22.1	9	3	3	3	3	6	3	3	0	0	
22W	Wastewater	22.6	9	3	3	3	2	7	3	3	1	0	
22W	Wastewater	22.7	9	3	3	3	0	9	3	3	3	1	
22W	Wastewater	22.11	9	3	3	3	1	8	3	3	2	2	
7R	River	7.1	9	3	3	3	2	7	2	3	2	1	
7R	River	7.2	9	3	3	3	3	6	3	3	0	0	
11R	River	11.1	0	EXCLUDED*									
11R	River	11.2	9	3	3	3	0	9	3	3	3	0	
17R	River	17.2	10	2	3	5	0	10	2	3	5	5	
21R	River	21.1	9	3	2	4	0	9	3	2	4	4	
24R	River	24.1	9	3	3	3	1	8	2	3	3	3	
24R	River	24.2	10	3	3	4	0	10	3	3	4	0	
24R	River	24.3	10	3	3	4	0	10	3	3	4	1	
24R	River	24.4	10	2	3	5	0	10	2	3	5	5	
24R	River	24.5	9	3	3	3	0	9	3	3	3	1	
0R	River	30.1	9	3	3	3	0	9	3	3	3	1	
			256	82	83	90	57	199	69	78	52	30	

Figure S2 Images of plastic particles collected from research sites: wastewater and river water. Particles from wastewater are outlined in red, while particles from the river are outlined in blue. Particles selected for microbiological analyses are marked with a green circle, and those selected for electron and fluorescence imaging are marked with a pink circle.

Figure S3 Example of growth obtained on the chromogenic medium supplemented with carbapenem. The medium was inoculated with 0.1 mL of suspension/suspension dilution obtained after detaching the biofilms from the plastic particles.

Table S2 Characteristics of isolates with confirmed phenotypic resistance to carbapenems (Imipenem). The left part of the table (to the left of the dividing line) shows strain metadata, while the right part presents antibiotic susceptibility test results in the form of inhibition zone diameters. Values indicating resistance to the antibiotic are marked in red. Combinations not included in the EUCAST guidelines are marked as "n.a."

Source	Site	Piece	Plastic type	Isolate ID	Species	IMP	PRL	CAZ	ATM	CIP	TOB	SXT
River	7R	7.1.W	PE	7.1.8	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	17	n.a	26	31	32	n.a	17
River	17R	17.2.W	PE	17.2.4	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	16	n.a	12	11	30	n.a	0
River	17R	17.2.W	PE	17.2.5	<i>A. veronii</i>	11	n.a	25	31	37	n.a	21
River	17R	17.2.W	PE	17.2.7	<i>A. veronii</i>	17	n.a	24	36	30	n.a	18
River	17R	17.2.W	PE	17.2.8	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	17	n.a	28	36	32	n.a	18
River	17R	17.2.W	PE	17.2.9	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	17	n.a	28	39	35	n.a	25
River	21R	21.1.W	Nylon/EVA	21.1.5	<i>A. veronii</i>	12	n.a	28	36	32	n.a	25
River	21R	21.1.W	Nylon/EVA	21.1.7	<i>A. veronii</i>	18	n.a	28	38	35	n.a	21
River	21R	21.1.W	Nylon/EVA	21.1.8	<i>A. sobria</i>	14	n.a	27	34	36	n.a	20
River	21R	21.1.W	Nylon/EVA	21.1.10	<i>A. veronii</i>	17	n.a	29	38	24	n.a	22
River	24R	24.1.W	PS	24.1.6	<i>A. veronii</i>	18	n.a	28	35	38	n.a	30
River	24R	24.1.W	PS	24.1.8	<i>A. veronii</i>	18	n.a	29	35	32	n.a	21
River	24R	24.1.W	PS	24.1.10	<i>A. salmonicida</i>	17	n.a	22	22	33	n.a	23
River	24R	24.3.W	PP	24.3.7	<i>A. veronii</i>	12	n.a	20	33	34	n.a	34
River	24R	24.4.W	PE	24.4.5	<i>A. veronii</i>	18	n.a	22	35	22	n.a	23
River	24R	24.4.W	PE	24.4.6	<i>P. putida</i>	16	22	19	18	28	21	n.a
River	24R	24.4.W	PE	24.4.8	<i>A. salmonicida</i>	18	n.a	22	18	34	n.a	22
River	24R	24.4.W	PE	24.4.9	<i>A. veronii</i>	18	n.a	28	35	38	n.a	30
River	24R	24.4.W	PE	24.4.10	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	17	n.a	20	23	37	n.a	14
River	24R	24.5.W	PE	24.5.7	<i>A. veronii</i>	15	n.a	21	25	28	n.a	25
Wastewater	0R	30.1.W	PET	30.1.7	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	16	n.a	0	0	22	n.a	17
Wastewater	2W	2.3.W	PP	2.3.10	<i>A. veronii</i>	17	n.a	26	22	27	n.a	25

Wastewater	6W	6.9.W	PP	6.9.3	<i>P. putida</i>	18	13	25	21	30	19	n.a
Wastewater	6W	6.11.W	PP	6.11.3	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	19	n.a	20	18	33	n.a	0
Wastewater	2W	6.11.W	PP	6.11.7	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	18	n.a	14	0	27	n.a	28
Wastewater	20W	20.6.W	PP	20.6.6	<i>S. maltophilia</i>	0	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	22
Wastewater	20W	20.11.W	PS	20.11.6	<i>S. maltophilia</i>	0	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	30
Wastewater	22W	22.7.W	Nylon/EVA	22.7.2	<i>S. maltophilia</i>	0	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	13
Wastewater	22W	22.11.W	PE	22.11.7	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	13	n.a	30	32	30	n.a	15
Wastewater	22W	22.11.W	PE	22.11.10	<i>A. hydrophila</i>	16	n.a	34	40	28	n.a	0

Table S3 List of primers used in PCR reactions along with their parameters.

Gene	Primers (5'-3')	Reference
<i>bla</i> _{KPC}	F: CGTCTAGTTCTGCTGTCTTG R: CTTGTCATCCTTGTTAGGCG	(Poirel et al., 2011)
<i>bla</i> _{NDM}	F: GGTTTGGCGATCTGGTTTTTC R: CGGAATGGCTCATCACGATC	
<i>bla</i> _{OXA-48}	F: GCGTGGTTAAGGATGAACAC R: CATCAAGTTCAACCCAACCG	
<i>bla</i> _{VIM}	F: GATGGTGTGGTTCGCATA R: CGAATGCGCAGCACCAG	
<i>bla</i> _{IMP}	F: GGAATAGAGTGGCTTAAyTCTC R: GGTTTAAyAAAACAACCACC	
<i>bla</i> _{SPM}	F: AAAATCTGGGTACGCAAACG R: ACATTATCCGCTGGAACAGG	
<i>bla</i> _{AIM}	F: CTGAAGGTGTACGGAAACAC R: GTTCGGCCACCTCGAATTG	
<i>bla</i> _{GIM}	F: TCGACACACCTTGGTCTGAA R: AACTTCCAACCTTGCCATGC	
<i>bla</i> _{BIC}	F: TATGCAGCTCCTTTAAGGGC R: TCATTGGCGGTGCCGTACAC	
<i>bla</i> _{SIM}	F: TACAAGGGATTCGGCATCG R: TAATGGCCTGTTCCCATGTG	
<i>bla</i> _{DIM}	F: GCTTGTCTTCGCTTGCTAACG R: CGTTCGGCTGGATTGATTG	
<i>bla</i> _{GES}	F: GCTTCATTACGCACTATT R: CGATGCTAGAAACCGCTC	(Hong et al., 2012)
<i>bla</i> _{IMI/NMC-A}	F: TGCGGTCGATTGGAGATAAA R: CGATTCTTGAAGCTTCTGCG	
<i>bla</i> _{C_{pha}/IMIS}	F: GCCTTGATCAGCGCTTCGTAGTG R: GCGGGGATGTCGCTGACGCAG	(Henriques et al., 2006)

Table S4 Physicochemical parameters of wastewater and river water collected from each research site (Site). Abbreviations: T – temperature, DO – dissolved oxygen, EC – electrical conductivity, Sal – salinity, ORP – redox potential, Turb – turbidity.

Source	Site	T	DO	EC	Sal	pH	ORP	Turb
Wastewater	2W	24.2	1.07	1141	0.57	7.32	423.1	3.75
	3W	23.5	5.45	1320	0.66	7.81	439.6	5.13
	5W	23	0.36	1077	0.53	7.46	407.7	7.55
	6W	21.5	1.07	744	0.36	7.57	417	1.86
	12W	21.9	3.93	1159	0.57	7.92	435.5	2.9
	20W	20.2	1.33	1231	0.61	8.1	296.8	42.13
	22W	19.2	1.31	1792.5	0.91	8.08	416.8	2.99
River	7R	24.1	4.77	401.4	0.19	8.37	421.3	12.67
	11R	26.3	7.95	370.9	0.18	8.7	416.6	14.37
	17R	23.4	3.97	390	0.19	8.2	438.9	4.91
	21R	27.1	6.85	394.7	0.18	8.57	424.2	2.9
	24R	28	5.92	390.2	0.19	8.63	424.7	7.79
	0R	22.8	7.08	418.9	0.2	8.31	414.7	28.8

Table S5 Spearman correlation results between size-related parameters (length and estimated surface area) and bacterial counts obtained under different incubation conditions: at 22 °C, 37 °C, and on carbapenem-supplemented medium. Results are presented both per particle (per piece) and normalized to surface area (per surface).

	length (mm)	surface (mm ²)	22 per piece	37 per piece	Carba per piece	22 per surface	37 per surface	Carba per surface
length (mm)		9.01E-09	0.085047	0.081884	0.3286	0.086896	0.065133	0.038317
surface (mm ²)	0.83582		0.057319	0.055651	0.23875	0.054668	0.035143	0.02166
22 per piece	0.31969	0.35083		1.30E-10	3.00E-12	3.80E-05	0.000597	0.000291
37 per piece	0.3228	0.35306	0.8812		2.47E-13	0.0002	8.65E-05	0.000307
Carba per piece	0.18467	0.22183	0.91045	0.92558		7.42E-06	1.25E-05	1.65E-06
22 per surface	-0.31791	-0.35439	0.67831	0.62848	0.71955		4.48E-17	5.41E-15
37 per surface	-0.34105	-0.38598	0.59021	0.65473	0.70709	0.9604		2.21E-15
Carba per surface	-0.38002	-0.41762	0.61586	0.61408	0.75211	0.94382	0.94738	

Figure S4 Quantitative representation of taxa included in the analyses. Isolates reliably identified only to the genus level are labeled with the suffix sp. (high genus-level match scores in MALDI-TOF and/or 16S rRNA gene sequencing). Isolates showing high similarity thresholds at the species level are characterized at the species level (high species-level match scores in MALDI-TOF analysis). Numbers above the bars indicate the number of isolates originating from wastewater (in red) and from the river (in blue)

confocal microscopy
SYTO 9 (S) + propidium iodide (P) with transmitted light imaging (T)

Figure S5 Confocal microscopy image showing fungal hyphae characterized by distinct V-shaped branching and oval-shaped structures, potentially representing sporangia. The image was captured from the surface of plastic particle 2.6.W. Confocal channels include SYTO-9 fluorescence (S), propidium iodide (P), transmitted light (T), and a merged composite (S+P+T).

Figure S6 Surface of particle 2.6.W, focusing on the morphology of fungal hyphae observed on the plastic surface. Hyphal fusion is visible.

Figure S7 Detailed view of particle 2.6.W showing dense, net-like fungal hyphal networks attached to the plastic surface, indicating active colonization.

Figure S8 Light microscopy observations of Gram-stained preparations for pieces collected from sites 2W, 6W and 22W, made from the same biofilm suspensions used for microbiological culturing

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